

PAU indicated PMS lines had mid-early duration (104-106 d); seed set percentage ranged from 8.2 (PMS-2 A) to 18.5% (PMS-10 A). □

Yield potential

Hormonal signals from root to shoot in xylem sap of rice plants in drying soil

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We compared changes in soil moisture and root water status in horizontally divided, differentially treated root systems of rice plants with changes in leaf water potential, leaf conductance, contents of free and bound abscisic acid (ABA), and cytokinins in the shoot xylem. ABA is a hormone that signals water deficit in soil and closes stomata. Cytokinins are antagonists of ABA as regards stomatal closure.

Seeds of rice cultivar IR36 were sown in sandy loam with 48% humus and raised in growth chambers. Seedlings were transplanted 3 wk after sowing in small plastic pots that fit into a Scholander chamber. We allowed roots that protruded from the bottom of the pots to grow in nutrient solution in beakers below the pots. Three weeks after transplanting, three stress treatments were started: 1) soil and protruding roots kept moist (control), 2) soil unwatered, but protruding roots kept moist, and 3) both soil and protruding roots unwatered for 30 h (water-stressed plants). Soil and protruding roots from treatment 3 were rewatered after 30 h.

Contents of free and bound ABA and cytokinins (2iP + 2iPA and t-Z + t-ZR equivalents) in xylem sap of well-watered, water-stressed, and rewatered rice seedlings.

Treatment	Free ABA (pmol/ml)	Bound ABA (pmol/ml)	2iP + 2iPA equivalent (pmol/ml)	t-Z + t-ZR equivalent (pmol/ml)
Well-watered	7.2 ± 1	73 ± 7.5	3.7	0.9
Water-stressed	92 ± 3	499 ± 75	0.8	0.2
Rewatered	52 ± 12	87 ± 5.7	1.9	0.3

Treatment 2 reduced soil moisture from 30 to 14% within 96 h, but did not alter leaf ψ_w (see figure). When soil moisture decreased below 14%, leaf and stem ψ_w sharply declined, indicating the onset of drought stress. Although the water potential of the shoot did not change when soil moisture ranged from 30 to 14%, leaf conductance decreased by about 50%. This decrease was inversely related to the content of free ABA in the xylem which was measured by radioimmunoassay. The increase of ABA in the xylem probably was root-sourced because the shoot was not drought-stressed during this phase of soil drying.

Prolonged (96-144 h) soil drying from 14 to 6% soil moisture resulted in a further decline in conductance, accompanied by a further threefold increase in ABA. At this stage the shoot was under drought stress. The additional ABA presumably was formed in the shoot and redistributed within the whole plant via phloem and xylem.

Xylem sap contained considerable amounts of bound ABA, the level of which increased during soil drying (treatment 3) and decreased again with rewatering (see table). In contrast, cytokinin levels (isopentenyladenine + isopentenyladenosine equivalents and trans-zeatin + trans-zeatinriboside equivalents [2 iP + 2iPA and t-Z + t-ZR equivalents]), measured by an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay, decreased during soil drying and increased again after rewatering. As cytokinins promote stomatal opening, their quantitative change may also explain observed changes in conductance.

The results provide evidence that rice roots sense soil moisture and send ABA as a hormonal signal to the shoot, which reacts by closing the stomata, and cytokinins as a hormonal signal to open

Changes in leaf conductance, leaf and stem water potential, and xylem ABA content of rice seedlings with upper roots in drying soil and lower roots in water.

stomata. Stomatal closure in response to ABA, and possibly by other adaptive processes, occurs before shoot water deficit develops. Further studies are necessary to elucidate the mechanism of root-to-shoot communication in rice under field conditions. □

Performance of *Oryza sativa* L. varieties under upland field conditions in Papua New Guinea (PNG)

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We evaluated rice genotypes Tambu (Senis/C12), Wantok (Senis/C22), Niupela (a selection from E1 from Indonesia), Senis (a selection from IR20), BR12-5-5-1-1 (developed in PNG), NG8297 (IR9728-2-2-2-2), NG8304 (IR13429-196-1-20), NG8313 (IR46), NG8315 (IR54), and NG8321 (IR4744-295-2-3) under upland field conditions during 1991 in Markham Valley, Morobe Province, PNG.

The soil is fine loam overlying silty loam and deep gravel. Vegetation is predominantly *Imperata cylindrica* with *Ophiuros* spp. and *Digitaria* spp. Annual rainfall averages 1,400 mm.

We dibbled 5-6 seeds/hill at 20- × 20-cm spacing, keeping sowing depth uniform. Each genotype was planted on 15 m². The experiment was laid out in a completely randomized block design with five replications. We recorded yield data for 100 hills (4 m² net area)/genotype per replication and yield components for 20 hills/genotype per replication. Data from only three of the replications showed consistency and were used for analysis of variance.

Tambu, Wantok, Niupela, NG8313, and NG8315 significantly outyielded the other genotypes (see table). They also

Yield and yield components of rice varieties under upland field condition in Gaidusen, Markham Valley, Morobe Province, PNG, 1991.^a

Variety	Yield (t/ha)	Plant ht (cm)	Productive tillers (no./hill)	Panicle length (cm)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	Panicle fertility (%)	Harvest index (%)	1000-grain wt (g)
Tambu	2.4 a	70.3 a	20.4 a	21.8 a	44.1 e	39.5 b	0.5 e	16.0 c
Wantok	2.3 a	70.6 b	19.7 a	21.0 a	42.7 c	41.3 b	0.4 e	17.2 c
Niupela	2.7 a	112.5 a	11.5 c	22.5 a	73.7 a	50.9 a	0.5 e	13.7 d
Senis	1.2 b	74.6 b	12.6 b	21.4 a	26.8 d	23.5 d	0.6 d	15.9 c
BR12-5-5-1-1	0.6 c	71.7 b	16.6 b	21.2 a	38.6 c	46.9 a	0.4 e	14.2 d
NG8297	1.1 b	74.2 b	15.5 b	21.2 a	32.1 d	31.5 c	0.7 c	17.2 c
NG8304	1.2 b	73.1 b	14.2 b	20.1 a	28.1 d	29.0 c	0.9 c	19.1 b
NG8313	2.7 a	82.1 b	24.0 a	20.1 a	58.1 b	49.5 a	1.7 a	16.5 c
NG8315	2.4 a	58.1 c	19.3 a	20.1 a	21.2 e	22.4 d	1.8 a	24.7 a
NG8321	1.5 b	58.2 c	11.0 c	20.7 a	31.5 d	39.7 b	1.2 b	19.4 b
CV (%)	14.5							

^a In a column, figures followed by different letters significantly differ at the 5% level by DMRT.

outperformed the others in yield components, such as productive tillers/hill, filled grains/panicle, harvest index, and 1,000-grain weight.

These genotypes will be tested in different agroecological zones before they are recommended for general cultivation in the country. □

Pest resistance—diseases

Reaction of rice genotypes of different origins and genealogy to blast (B1) disease in Nigeria

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Rice B1 *Pyricularia grisea* is a major constraint to rice production in Africa. Its severity is greatest in the uplands, rainfed lowlands, and inland valleys of West Africa and in the cold-prone mid-altitude areas in the East, Central, and Southern Africa sub-region.

We screened 1,253 lines and best local check varieties for reaction to B1 at an upland site at IITA, (7° N, 3° E, and 200 m above sea level) with reliably high B1 levels. The lines were entries in various INGER-Africa nurseries in 1991 and in the International Rice Blast Nursery (IRBN). The B1 screening plot was laid out to conform with the IRBN plot design.

Analysis of *Standard evaluation system for rice* B1 score data revealed that of the 266 entries in the upland nurseries,

Adapted upland rice varieties common in the ancestry of B1-resistant lines.^a

Variety	Origin	Lines developed (no.)
<i>Adapted varieties or progenitor</i>		
Colombia 1	Colombia	32
Dourado Precoce	Brazil	18
Eloni	Surinam	17
Iguape Cateto	Brazil	12
LAC23	Liberia	8
Moroberekan	West Africa	17
OS6	Zaire	7
Palawan	Philippines	14
63-83	Cote d'Ivoire	19
<i>Modern varieties</i>		
IAC25	Brazil	12
IR13149-19-1	IIRI	9
IRAT104	Cote d'Ivoire	21
IRAT112	Cote d'Ivoire	12
IRAT113	Cote d'Ivoire	34
IRAT212	IITA	17
ITA235	IITA	10
M312A	Cote d'Ivoire	32
TOx7	IITA	8
TOx1010	IITA	19
TOx1367-7	IITA	15
TOx1780	IITA	8
Total		341

^a Of 1,253 entries screened, 580 were recorded as B1 resistant. Among these, more than 59% were derived from the adapted varieties listed above.

145 scored 0-1 and only four scored 7-9. Of the 268 entries in the irrigated nurseries, 24 scored 0-1 and 55 scored 7-9. Of the 539 entries in both African and global B1 nurseries, 108 scored 0-1 and 110 scored 7-9.

Most entries in the irrigated and rainfed lowland nurseries had intermediate scores of 4-6 (see figure, a). In the upland nurseries, however, entries with scores of 0-3 had the highest frequency. Similarly, many entries in the